

METHOD FOR ENABLING HIGHLY LOADABLE MATERIAL COMBINATIONS OF PP AND ALUMINUM WITHOUT THE USE OF ADHESIVES

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Keywords: Short fibre thermoplastics, joining, hybrid materials

ABSTRACT

The joining of polymers to metal without the use of adhesives is of interest because this will make the use of chemical agents at least in this manufacturing step redundant. In the automotive industry polymer-metal-hybrid parts are of high interest because they combine a high functional integration with a low weight. Here the joining becomes possible due to a finely structured surface of the metal parts which in turn are used as inserts in the injection molding process. The structure is achieved with a pulsed laser and thus variable in depth, width and generated undercuts. No overmolding i.e. contact of polymer to both sides of the metal is necessary. To achieve an optimal interlocking of structured surface with the polymer a heating-up of the metal inserts preferably using induction heating is useful.

The method presented here gives results on par with adhesives. Loads on the joining area are more evenly distributed due to the interlocking surfaces of polymer and metal than e.g. using adhesives. Thus the joining is extremely resistant to thermal loading and shows no peel effects at the boundary of the joint areas.

We will show that favorable results persist not only directly after manufacturing but also after corrosion and cyclic temperature tests under different load conditions.

This new method is a viable process for the production of not only cost-efficient but also lightweight semi structural polymer-metal-hybrid parts e.g. in the automotive industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

The efforts to achieve economically feasible light weight structures e.g. for automobiles lead to the need of better joining techniques. In the case of metals and polymers today this is in most cases overmolding or bonding using an additional adhesive. Each of these techniques has specific disadvantages as for overmolding the metal part has to be accessible by both sides and adhesives add a further chemical compound that may be undesirable due to given environmental or other standards.

Here we present a novel method to join polymers and metals, which overcomes these drawbacks by structuring the metal side of the joint and bring it into contact with the polymer in the injection molding process without the use of additional materials of any kind. This results in a joint which has a high bonding strength which does not deteriorate in corrosive environments or after alternating thermal loads.

2 THE NEW JOINING METHOD

The joining is done in two steps. The first is to structure the metal part, here a surface of an aluminium test specimen, with a high power short pulsed laser. A result with the height profile is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Detail of structured surface of an aluminum test specimen

On a more detailed level the aluminium surface looks more arbitrarily structured. This is because the nanosecond pulsed laser melts and evaporates the aluminium on a tiny focus spot of the surface giving way to a melt pool. The melt pool is under the evaporation pressure and thus the melted aluminium is ejected. Due to the small mass and the therefore small heat content the aluminium freezes instantaneously in the free air, see figure 2 with a polished micrograph section.

Figure 2: Polished micrograph section of aluminum surface after laser-structuring

The structured surface needs no further preparation prior to the injection molding process, especially no cleaning is necessary, also the structuring may be done weeks in advance.

In the course of the project the parameters of the laser (i.e. pulse energy, pulse frequency, velocity on the surface, ablation rate) used to structure the surface have been systematically changed in order to get the most efficient structure.

The second step is the injection molding process. In this step the small pits in the surface are filled with the polymer material, here we chose a 30% LGF reinforced PP, and a strong interlocking of the two materials follows.

Figure 3: CT-scan of aluminum surface after injection molding.

For the strength and performance of the joint it is important that the pits are not only filled by matrix material but also with the embedded glass fibers, see figure 3. In this way the load is not only transferred by the matrix material alone but also by the much stiffer and stronger glass fibers. An important question in our research was a possible positive effect on the interface strength of an inductive heating of the aluminum plates during the injection molding process.

3 TEST SETUP

The tests were performed with tests specimens consisting of a polymer rib on a flat metal plate, see figure 4. The full joint area had been laser structured prior to the injection molding process.

Figure 1: Test specimen consisting of (glass-fibre reinforced) polymer on a 40mm × 70mm large aluminum plate.

After injection molding the tests specimens underwent shear and pull-off tests at different temperatures to determine the performance of the new joint, see figure 5 for the test-setup in the pull-off test. The specimens also underwent temperature cycling tests and corrosion tests, both of these treatments in accordance with automotive norms. Following this artificial aging, the specimens were also tested.

Figure 5: Test-setup for pull-off test at room temperature.

4 RESULTS

In this part we show the results of the joint strength for PP-LGF30 in combination with aluminum plates. In figure 6 and figure 7 the results for the pull-off and the shear tests are shown. The colors signify the different methods used in the production of the tests specimen. For the medium and dark colored columns the aluminum was heavily structured as shown in figure 2. For the medium colored columns less energy was applied with the laser resulting in a smoother structured surface.

Figure 6: Results for pull-off tests at different configurations.

Induction was used to heat up the aluminum plates to about 120 °C directly in the injection-molding tool for the light and dark colored columns.

Figure 7: Results for shear tests at different configurations.

Most significant in these results is the excellent performance of the joint after artificial aging (temperature cycling and corrosion treatment). The difference between the parts made with and without the use of induction is small. The failure of the joint gives different pictures at different temperatures. PP-LGF30 with a weight content of 30 % glass fibres on aluminum shows the forming of filaments, see figure 8.

Figure 8: Pull-off test at 80 °C.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The method presented shows very good results for the joint strength between polymer and metal. Although the initial strength of the joint may be less than that achieved with an appropriate adhesive the resistance to aging makes this new method very competitive. Being the outcome of a research project the potential for optimization is still significant.

REFERENCES

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research of the project presented in this paper is funded in part by the German Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) in the WING-program with the title “ExtraLight – Extremer Leichtbau mit Kunststoff-Metall-Hybriden” with the grant codes 03X3037A, 03X3037H, 03X3037C, 03X3037E.